

INTERFACIAL STUDIES OF POLYLACTIC ACID (PLA)/FLAX BIOCOMPOSITE: FROM MODEL SURFACE TO FIBRE TREATMENT

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SUMMARY

A NaOH treatment on flax fibres was proposed and optimised to improve the interfacial adhesion between the reinforce fibre and a polylactic acid polymer matrix. AFM Force volume was used to qualitatively characterise the influence of the treatment on the fibres adhesion properties, and a model system, including a smooth PLA surface and a cellulose microbead was developed to quantitatively measure the contribution of van der Waals forces between these two materials.

Keywords: Polylactic acid, Flax fibre, Interface, Biocomposite, Atomic force Microscopy

INTRODUCTION

The drive for eco-friendly solutions has led to a renewed interest in the use of natural fibres in composite materials not only due to their interesting reinforcement properties, low density, low cost, and biodegradability, but also due to the fact that these materials can be considered as a vector of development for local agricultural resources in emerging countries [1,2]. Natural fibres such as flax, hemp, sisal and jute are environmentally friendly alternatives to the use of glass fibres as reinforcement in polymer based composites. Several works has been published on the mechanical properties of flax fibres-reinforced thermoplastic composites [3,4]. More recently, development of new “eco-biocomposites”, made from flax fibres reinforced biodegradable polymer matrix, such as polylactic acid (PLA) were developed [5-7]. It was reported that the specific Young's modulus of PLA/Flax biocomposite (6.52 ± 0.075 GPa for 25% in charge) can be as close to that of glass/polyester composites (7.762 ± 0.0638 GPa) [7], which makes them good candidates for plastics, automobile and packaging industries [8].

However, even if such biocomposites present interesting mechanical properties, one of the major drawbacks of natural fibres is their poor thermal stability, anisotropic mechanical performances, high moisture absorption and heterogeneity [9]. In addition the fibre-matrix adhesion, which is essential for a good transfer of the applied stress between the two materials, is generally poor due to the hydrophilic character of the fibres and the opposite hydrophobic character of polymeric matrices. Many attempts have been made to improve adhesion at the fibre-matrix interface, by chemically

modifying the surface of the fibre [9-11], by physical or physico-chemical treatments [12] or by using coupling agents or compatibilizers [13]. The efficiency of these treatments on the interfacial adhesion between the two materials were tested indirectly, using for example macro-scale mechanical tests [14], water sorption studies [15], or chemical analysis [16] etc. It should be underlined here the inherent difficulty in conducting experiments on real fibres due to their chemical and structural heterogeneities. Recent AFM images [17] demonstrated the highly heterogeneous topography of the flax fibres and the affected change in morphology and roughness following different chemical treatments. It is thus likely that coupled parameters, including chemical and physical modifications of the fibres, are responsible for these enhanced adhesion properties. Thus complementary techniques and works are still needed to improve our understanding of adhesion between the fibers and the matrix in natural fibre based biocomposite.

AFM colloid probe technique has been emerged as an important tool in quantitatively estimating intermolecular forces between two approaching surfaces by measuring force-distance curves [18]. The technique was, for example, extensively used to study interaction between cellulose surfaces in the pulp and paper industries [19]. Most of these experiments were mainly focussed on the preparation of ultra flat cellulose surfaces and smooth, spherical and non porous cellulose micro beads in order to mimic a sphere-plane interaction. Experiments performed in electrolyte solutions forwarded a better understanding of the interactions between various materials and additives in paper making.

In this work, we propose a two steps approach to better understand the adhesion forces between flax fibres and PLA matrix. In the first part, we will present AFM force volume (FV) images of raw and chemically modified flax fibres, in order to qualitatively map, at the nano-scale, the changes in the adhesion properties of the flax fibre following the alkali attack. A more quantitative study between a PLA surface and cellulose colloidal probe, using the colloidal force microscopy (CFM) technique, will be presented in the second part. The developed set-up allows to directly measure adhesion forces between the two materials which mimic our biocomposite system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

NaOH treatment of the flax fibres

An alkali treatment of flax fibres was performed and optimised to modify the fibres surface. Flax fibres were initially weighed and treated with 200 mL of (1%, 2%, 3%, 5% and 10%) of NaOH solutions for 20 minutes at 23°C. The fibres were then filtered and then washed throughly in Milli Q water and dried in Vacuum oven at 85 °C for 5 hours before any analysis.

AFM Force-Volume imaging

AFM experiments were performed using a Nanoscope IIIa multimode scanning probe microscope (Veeco, USA). Force-volume images were obtained from the deformation of the cantilever deflection at each point on the sample surface at a constant Z position of the sample, to give an adhesion map of the sample. Such images were acquired on various flax fibres in air by recording a 64×64 array of force–distance curves on a 1.75 × 1.75 μm^2 area, using the force–volume mode of the microscope. In this way, adhesion

forces were measured every 13.6 nm. Force maps were captured in "relative triggering mode", which ensure that the maximum cantilever deflection caused by the sample is the same in every force plot. The following parameters were used: $F_{\text{load}} = 92.8$ nN, a Z scan speed of 6.5 Hz and a FV scan rate of 0.025 Hz. The force volume data set combines nearly simultaneously measured topographic and force information into a single data set allowing testing for correlations between forces and surface features.

Colloid force measurements

Direct force measurements between PLLA films, glued on a magnetic stainless steel disk, and cellulose colloid probes were performed by cycles of approach and retraction of the piezotube. The exact value of the cantilever spring constant k was determined to be 51 N/m by the fundamental resonant frequency method. The velocity of the probe was kept constant at $3.5 \mu\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ during all the experiments and the number of data points was set to be 1500. To improve the measurement accuracy, statistical analysis of at least 400 force-distance curves at 10 different arbitrary surface sites were performed. The adhesion force measured was then normalised according to Derjaguin's approximation [20] by the radius of curvature of the colloidal probe and plotted as frequency distribution curves of normalised adhesion force (N/m).

A quantitative interpretation of colloidal force measurements is based on the assumption of a perfect sphere-plane geometry contact. Thus, two main prerequisites are necessary in colloid force microscopy (CFM), which include the preparation of molecularly smooth films and the preparation of a well defined micrometer size, spherical and non-porous colloidal particle. Detailed methods to prepare molecularly smooth PLA, cellulose films and microbeads are already presented elsewhere [21]. In short, smooth PLA films were made by spin coating a drop of 10 g/L PLA solution in dichloromethane on a freshly cleaved muscovite mica surface at 3000 rpm for 10 seconds (Figure 1). The roughness of the surface, as determined using AFM, was found to be around 0.2 nm on an area of $25 \mu\text{m}^2$. Cellulose thin films were also made by a similar spin coating process where, 0.5% of cellulose solution in LiCl/Dimethylacetamide solvent (9%) was spin coated on to freshly cleaved mica surface at 3000 rpm for a minute. The films were then dried at 160°C for 10 minutes and then rinsed in water to remove LiCl excess. The films were then dried at 100°C for 20 minutes. The roughness of the films was found to be around 4 nm over $25 \mu\text{m}^2$.

Cellulose microbeads were made by regenerating cellulose from cellulose triacetate (CTA) (Aldrich) microbeads [21]. Cellulose was regenerated from CTA microbeads by a saponification reaction, as verified by IR spectroscopy (Perkin Elmer). The microbeads were then collected by filtration, washed thoroughly in MilliQ-plus water and vacuum dried at 45°C for 3 days. A so-formed single microbead of cellulose, whose diameter was precisely determined using SEM images, was then glued (Loctite 3040) at the extreme end of an AFM cantilever tip. The glue was allowed to cure for 48 hours under ambient conditions.

Figure 1: Tapping mode (TM) AFM image ($5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$) of smooth PLA surface (a), corresponding cross-section (b). SEM image of the cellulose colloid probe (c) and TM-AFM imaging of the surface of the cellulose micro bead ($5 \times 5 \mu\text{m}^2$) (d).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

SEM and AFM images of the Flax fibres

SEM and the AFM images (Figure 2) of flax single fibres show that after the NaOH treatment, the fibre surface becomes smoother. AFM images allow to visualize long and oriented fibrils along the fiber main axis. These fibrils can be attributed to the arrangement of the cellulose micro-fibrils, as previously described by Balnois *et al.* [17]. It is further interesting to note that the oriented fibrils are better resolved when the alkali treatment is enhanced (Figure 2c), *i.e.* when the concentration of the reagent is increased. Furthermore, the number and size of the spherical (ellipsoid) shaped particles, that are present on non treated fibres (Figure 2a), clearly disappear with respect to the chemical treatment.

Figure 2: SEM and AFM images of flax fibres. Raw fibres (a), 3% NaOH treated (b) and 10% NaOH treated (c), corresponding phase and 3D height image (d1, d2).

Eventhough the exact composition of the particles cannot be given here, pectins are expected to be the predominant species at the fiber surface [22]. These observations prove the efficiency of the alkali treatment, especially at high concentration, to remove some chemical materials from the outer surface of raw fibers to give a smooth and homogeneous surface, on which cellulosic micro-fibrils can be observed.

AFM Force-volume imaging of the flax fibres

AFM Force-Volume imaging was carried out on both raw and chemically treated flax fibres (Figure 3). Figure 3a is an example of a FV image of the raw flax fibre. The image shows slight variation in softness of the sample surface, with altering light regions (soft materials) and dark rounded ones (hard materials). This FV image is typical of a heterogeneous material, and even though a quantitative interpretation of this force map is difficult, it contrasts with the FV image of the NaOH treated one. In this latter case, the FV image is showing a more homogeneous surface, on which a specific orientation of micro-fibrils can even be observed, in good correlation with the topographic image. Hence, from a qualitative point of view, the technique allows to demonstrate the efficiency of the alkali treatment to remove some particles from the raw fibre, to give a more homogeneous surface, from a topographical and adhesion point of view.

Figure 3: AFM Force-Volume images a) Raw flax fibre, b) 5% NaOH treated flax fibre.

Direct adhesion force measurements between cellulose and PLA

A more quantitative approach to determine the contribution of interaction forces between PLA and cellulose was conducted using the colloidal force microscopy. An example of a force-distance curve measured with our system is presented in (Figure 4). In the region of large separation, where the probe and sample do not interact, the cantilever is not deflected by external forces and the resulting force is equal to zero (position A). This part is called the “non-contact region”. On the approach stage, as the scanner Z position is increased, the cantilever and the sample start to interact which induce a cantilever deflection. The attractive interaction between the two objects trigger an instability of the probe which results in a jump of the probe onto the sample called “*jump into contact*”, (position B). Below this point, for incompressible surfaces, a repulsive force appears and linearly increases with the motion of the piezo-stage. This part (position C), which corresponds to a straight line in the deflection (or force) versus piezo displacement (or surface distance) curve, is called the “*constant compliance region or hard-wall contact*”. After Z scan reached a specified value, the deflection of the cantilever is switched in the opposite direction (attractive). In the absence of plastic deformation, the deflection observed during retraction of the cantilever follows the constant compliance region of the approach (position D). When the position of the cantilever reaches point E, in which the cantilever spring constant overcomes the adhesion force, the particles and surface separates and the probe “jumps-out” from the surface to its equilibrium position (position F). This transition is defined as the adhesion force and can be calculated by simply converting the cantilever deflection to the corresponding force value according to Hooke’s law:

$$F = -k \times \Delta z \quad (1)$$

Where k is the accurate cantilever spring constant and Δz is the cantilever deflection in the z direction.

Figure 4: An example of an AFM force-distance curve showing the characteristic features of interactions between two Surfaces: A) Non-contact region, B) Jump into contact, C) constant compliance region, D) adhesion event, E) jump-out and F) return to non-contact region.

Frequency distribution of the normalised adhesion force measurements between a flat PLA surface and cellulose probe under ambient conditions (RH 56%) is presented in the Figure 5. Owing to the homogeneity of the surfaces, narrow distribution of the adhesion forces was recorded. The frequency distribution of normalised adhesion force showed a maximum peak at 0.22 N/m.

Figure 5: Frequency distribution of normalised adhesion forces between PLA surface and cellulose colloid probes (RH 55%). Different curves in the graph shows the frequency distribution of the normalised adhesion force for different cellulose probes and PLA surfaces representing the reproducibility of the adhesion force measurements.

The total adhesion force between an AFM probe and a sample surface on a fundamental level is the sum of several forces including the capillary force (F_C) and the solid-solid interactions consisting of van der Waals force (F_{vdW}), electrostatic force (F_E), and the chemical bonding force (F_B). [23]

$$F_{adh} = F_{vdW} + F_C + F_E + F_B \quad (2)$$

In our investigated system, we assume that F_E and F_B is equal to zero. Thus the resulting adhesion force can be simplified as the contribution of the van der Waals and capillary forces.

$$F_{adh} = F_{vdW} + F_C \quad (3)$$

The contribution of the capillary force is known to be dependant on the relative humidity and become negligible when the relative humidity tends to zero percentage. At 0% of RH, it can be assumed that the contribution of the adhesion force comes entirely from van der Waals interaction. Hamaker proposed that the van der Waals interaction energy between two macroscopic bodies can be calculated by the summation of the individual interactions between all of the atomic or molecular pairs which make up those bodies [23]. For sphere-plane geometry, the van der Waals force can be expressed as:

$$F_{vdW} = -\frac{A_H R}{6D^2} \quad (4)$$

Where A_H is the Hamaker constant, R is the radius of curvature of the sphere, D is the separation distance between the two objects ($\sim 0.2\text{nm}$).

The frequency distribution of normalised adhesion forces between different systems at various percentage of relative humidity are shown in the Figure 6. For cellulose bead-PLA film contact, F_{vdW}/R was experimentally found to be 0.16 N/m at RH 2%. Where as, for the cellulose-cellulose system, the normalised adhesion forces at RH 55% and RH 2% were 0.83 N/m and 0.23 N/m respectively. First of all, these graphs show the importance of capillary forces in both systems but this effect is even more pronounced for the cellulose-cellulose interaction. This result is expected owing to the hydrophilic character of the cellulose in comparison with PLA. Secondly, when looking at the interaction forces of these two systems at 2% of humidity, when the main contribution comes from van der Waals forces, we can conclude that the cellulose-cellulose interaction is greater than the PLA-cellulose interaction.

Figure 6: Frequency distribution of normalised adhesion forces between PLA film-cellulose probe and cellulose film-cellulose probe at relative humidity RH 2% (a) and at relative humidity RH 55% (b).

The Hamaker constant calculated for the interaction between cellulose and PLA across air was calculated from the equation (4) and compared with the Hamaker constant calculated from the Lifshitz theory [23] as shown in the table 1.

Table 1. Comparison between experimental and calculated Hamaker constant for different systems including PLA, Cellulose and air

Material 1	Material 2	Medium	Calculated $A_H (\times 10^{-20}\text{J})$	Experimental $A_H (\times 10^{-20}\text{J})$
Cellulose	Cellulose	Air	8.4	5.35 (this work)
Cellulose	PLLA	Air	5.8	3.84 (this work)

Even if differences can be observed between theoretical and experimental Hamaker constants for the investigated systems, it should be noticed here that the A_H value for

cellulose-PLLA interactions were lower than the one for cellulose-cellulose interaction. This result demonstrates that the adhesion between cellulose and PLA is weaker than that for cellulose-cellulose. This finding is expected due to the different polar properties of the two materials, PLA (hydrophobic) and cellulose (hydrophilic). An optimisation of the interaction between these two components is therefore a key parameter to enhance the mechanical properties of such biocomposites.

Conclusion

A NaOH treatment of flax fibres was proposed and optimised to improve the interfacial adhesion with the PLA matrix. AFM Force-volume imaging technique was used to map the adhesion properties of the raw and the NaOH treated flax fibres. Quantitative study of the interfacial interactions between the different materials in PLA/flax biocomposite was performed using the colloid probe microscopy technique. Direct adhesion measurements between a flat polylactic acid surface and a cellulose microbead have shown the importance of the capillary forces when experiments were carried out under ambient conditions (RH = 56%, T = 23°C) and allows us to separate the contribution of van der Waals forces when RH was extrapolated at 0%. Our results, through the calculation of the Hamaker constant, shows that the van der Waals interaction forces, for the PLA / cellulose / air system, are lower than those obtained for the cellulose / cellulose / air system and hence underline the importance of optimising the interface between these materials.

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